

Tutoring and mentoring Industrial Engineering and Management freshman-students in Project-Based Learning

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15874064>

Abstract

Tutors and mentors are key supporting first-year students in Project-Based Learning (PBL), especially in engineering education. This study explores the roles of faculty tutors and alumni mentors in a first-year PBL course at the University of Minho, gathering feedback from students and those in support roles. A case study approach was used, combining two online questionnaires – one for students and another for tutors and mentors. Students rated their tutors and mentors across several dimensions: communication, availability, support, and motivation. Additional insights were gathered through open comments and focus group discussions. Results showed that both roles were appreciated but seen as different. Recent graduates as mentors often received slightly higher scores in team motivation and emotional support. Tutors were more closely linked to academic guidance and peer assessment. Only one item related to peer feedback was rated higher for tutors. Tutors and mentors generally found the experience rewarding but pointed out challenges with student engagement. The study highlights the importance of clearly defining each role from the start. Combining academic and peer-level support enhances the learning experience and may help first-year students navigate PBL more confidently.

Keywords: Active Learning; Project-Based Learning; Industrial Engineering and Management Education.

1 Introduction

There is an ongoing discussion on integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education (Majeed & Hwang, 2024; Rahayu, 2023; Ravaglia, 2024). Simultaneously in industry, human-centric approach is strongly emphasized and it is one of the pillars for Industry 5.0 (Breque et al., 2021). At first, these ideas might seem at odds and a paradox: AI in education and human-centric in industry, bringing AI into classrooms while insisting on keeping people at the centre of industrial development. The education and industry world are using common tools, shared challenges, and the need for more integrated thinking. They are closer than before, and need to be, particular, in an Engineering Education context. Importantly, embracing new tools and methods does not imply abandoning the strengths of traditional practices, namely, demanding excellent teachers and tutors.

In Engineering Education, where active learning methodologies are increasingly being implemented, using traditional and recent tools (Alves & van Hattum-Janssen, 2022; Lima et al., 2024), teachers and tutors remain the most important knowledge source. They are emphatic, have a sacred trust (Schmier, 2001), and are flexible, helping students in this new Volatile, Uncertain, Complex, and Ambiguous (VUCA) world and, at the same time, Brittle, Anxious, Nonlinear, and Incomprehensible (BRITE) world (Figueiredo, 2023).

In Project-Based Learning (PBL), an active and centred-student learning methodology, it is recognized that a tutor has a critical role (Fernandes et al., 2009; Grunefeld & Silén, 2000; Powell, 2004; Powell & Weenk, 2003; Simão et al., 2008; Weenk et al., 2004). In particular, in Project-Led Engineering Education (PLEE), Powell and Weenk (2003) referred to what students can expect from the tutor:

- Keep to agreements made and promptly follow up on previously agreed actions;
- Read submitted parts of reports, logbooks, and worksheets quickly;

- Should not be too directive - he facilitates progress and does not solve the teams' problems himself;
- Be honest and do not always say everything is fine, especially when not;
- Be prepared to consider other opinions;
- Consult with other PLEE tutors as necessary;
- Gives positive feedback.

According to Simão et al. (2015), tutelage in Higher Education can be done by teachers included or not in the curricular units (CU) of the semester, researchers, or upper classes students. In addition, various kinds of tutoring, such as mentoring, curricular tutoring, academic tutoring, and training-related tutoring, have been implemented by Higher Educational Institutions as a response to the needs diagnosed among students (Simão et al., 2008). Although similar, tutoring and mentorship have differences (Colvin & Ashman, 2010; Lorenzetti et al., 2019; Terrion & Leonard, 2007). While peer tutoring typically focuses on a more advanced student helping lower-level students with course content, peer mentoring focuses on a more experienced student helping a less experienced student improve overall academic performance, encourages mentors' personal growth, and provides advice, support, and knowledge to the mentee (Colvin & Ashman, 2010).

Tutoring has always been a requisite of PBL implemented since 2004_05 in the first year of Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) at the University of Minho (Alves et al., 2012; Lima et al., 2007). This tutoring suffered three main changes: 1) only one tutor by a team that was a teacher of a CU (Alves, Sousa, Fernandes, et al., 2016; Alves et al., 2007; Alves et al., 2010; Fernandes et al., 2009), 2) only faculty member, not teacher in this particular year, 3) a faculty member and a third year student by each team (Alves, Moreira, Leão, et al., 2017; Leão et al., 2022).

Pursuing a continuous improvement journey involving action-research cycles (Alves et al., 2020; Alves, Moreira, Fernandes, et al., 2017; Alves & Leão, 2015) motivates these changes. This paper appears as a consequence of this journey. It presents and compares the tutoring by a faculty member and mentoring by IEM alumni from students' perspectives, which support the teams' academic development in a PBL context. In addition, it presents the tutoring experience from the faculty members' and mentors' perspectives.

This paper is organized into six sections. After this first section, section 2 presents the materials and methods used to collect feedback for the study. Section 3 offers an overview of the IEM first-year, first-semester, focused in Integrated Project in IEM and tutor role and functions on this curricular unit. Section 4 presents the students' results and feedback regarding the role of tutors and mentors. Section 5 presents the tutors and mentors perspective regarding their tutelage experience. Finally, the last section draws conclusions based on the findings.

2 Materials and methods

The research strategy employed in this paper was a case study focusing on the 2024/2025 cohort of 70 students enrolled in the first semester of the first year of the IEM Bachelor's program. To gather student's perspectives, the research team administered an online questionnaire at the end of the semester. This questionnaire, "Learning by project: tutor's assessment," is available in Alves et al. (2017). One of the initial questions in the questionnaire asked students to indicate which type of tutor they were evaluation – either a faculty member or an IEM alumni. It is composed of a total of 37 questions divided into 10 sections. The closed items (34) are scored on a Likert scale [1: Totally disagree to 5: Totally agree]. The remaining three items were open questions.

In addition, the results of a focus group developed in the final workshop were used to examine various dimensions, including the tutor's role topic. Twenty-four students, one tutor and two teachers participate in this focus group. Figure 1 presents a moment of the final workshop where students work in groups on the dimensions more critical during the PBL process: 1) Peer review; 2) Report assessment by groups; 3) Role of

the tutor; 4) Integration of the curricular units into the project; 5) IEM@ProjectNetworking; and 6) Support and feedback from teachers.

Figure 1. Focus groups during the final workshop

Seventy-one fulfilled the questionnaires, 33 regarding the tutor role and 38 regarding the mentor role, which represents a 51% response rate. For this kind of study, that is enough to examine the results and compare the two types of tutelage. While more answers would be better, these still show students felt about the support they received. Furthermore, to collect the tutors' and mentors' perspectives, a different online-questionnaire, "Tutor experience evaluation," was used, which is also available in Alves et al. (2017). This questionnaire was divided into seven sections and has 22 items. Six were open questions. Fourteen completed questionnaires were obtained (only two faculty members did not fulfill the questionnaire), corresponding to an 88% response rate.

The main research questions focused on this study are:

1. What are the students' perspectives regarding the performance of tutors/mentors in PBL context?
2. Do tutors and mentors play tutors' role similarly?
3. How was the tutoring/mentoring experience?

3 Study context

The Bachelor's Degree in Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) at the University of Minho introduced Project-Based Learning (PBL) in the 2004-2005 academic year as a way to make learning more engaging and practical (Alves et al., 2020; Alves et al., 2021; Lima et al., 2007). It started with interdisciplinary projects in the first semester and became a formal part of the curriculum in 2012-2013, with the course Integrated Project in Industrial Engineering and Management I (IPIEM1). This course brings together knowledge from different disciplines within the IEM program (Alves et al., 2014).

Over the years, the course has evolved. Adjustments were made to improve how it runs and to better support students and teachers (Alves, Sousa, Moreira, et al., 2016; Alves, Moreira, Fernandes, et al., 2017). Table 1 lists all the Project Supporting Courses (PSCs) involved in the latest editions of IPIEM1. These courses come from two schools (Sciences and Engineering) and three departments (Mathematics, Production and Systems, and Information Technologies).

Table 1. Courses of the 1st year, 1st semester, of the IEM program

Regime	Curricular Unit	Scientific Area	ECTS
Year 1			60
S1	Calculus for Engineering	M	5
S1	Computer Programming I	CE	5
S1	Integrated Project in Industrial Engineering and Management I	EIS	5
S1	Introduction to Economics Engineering	EIS	5
S1	Introduction to Industrial Engineering and Management	EIS	5
S1	Linear Algebra for Engineering	M	5

Through learning by doing, students connect technical knowledge to real-world situations. This method supports deeper learning and helps students retain knowledge over time. In addition to the technical skills from the PSCs, students also develop transversal skills like teamwork, communication, conflict management and critical-thinking. Although challenging, the PBL experience gives students many opportunities to grow in both academic and soft skill areas.

3.1 Integrated Project in Industrial Engineering and Management 1

The IPIEM1 is a project-based course where students work in teams, supported by tutors, to solve real-world problems. Each team, typically made up of seven to nine students, develops a project often focused on sustainability (Alves, Moreira, Leão, et al., 2017; Alves et al., 2024; Colombo et al., 2015; Moreira et al., 2011). Along the way, students apply technical knowledge from different subjects and develop various transversal skills such as teamwork, creativity, and conflict management.

Each team receives the Project Guide at the start of the semester to guide their work. This document, prepared by the coordination team, outlines how the IPIEM1 is organized and what is expected from students and tutors. It includes: 1) an overview of the IPIEM1 model and key references; 2) the list of coordinators, teachers, and tutors, and their contact details; 3) the project theme and main goals; 4) a description of the tutors' roles; 5) learning outcomes for each PSC; 6) the assessment model for both IPIEM1 and the PSCs; 7) information about resources available (e.g. project rooms); and 8) details about the e-learning platform used in the course.

Throughout the semester, feedback is collected from students, teachers, tutors and educational researchers to monitor the project's progress and improve the learning process. At the end of the semester, a final workshop is held. In this workshop, survey results, assessment outcomes, and reflections on the project experience are discussed. The workshop begins with small group discussions, following focus group principles, and ends with a collective sharing of ideas and conclusions.

3.2 Tutor role and functions

In the 2024/2025 edition, each student team was supported by one faculty tutor and one alumni mentor. The tutor is a faculty member from the Department of Production and Systems (DPS), who was not involved in teaching first-year courses of that semester. The mentor, IEM alumni, brought a professional perspective; sharing insights from industry and helping students navigate their first-year experience. All eight alumni mentors had completed their degrees within the past five years, and all but one had taken part in IPIEM1 PBL as students. Having previously worked with tutors during their first year, they could now support new students from a peer and professional standpoint. Both roles were taken on voluntarily and offered different but complementary support forms.

The faculty tutor played a more academic and procedural role. According to the Project Guide, their responsibilities included:

- Monitoring the team's progress of the project and the development of relevant skills.
- Supporting the peer assessment process by explaining how to apply the criteria and use the required tools.
- Reviewing the individual peer assessments and discussing the outcomes with the team to encourage fair and honest evaluation.
- Observing individual contributions to identify students who might be struggling.
- Reporting the team's progress to the coordination team and passing along any updates or concerns.
- Communicating with PSC teachers about specific academic difficulties observed in the team.

The IEM *alumni* mentors offered informal and peer-level support. They helped students adjust to university life, explained how to access services, and encouraged good team dynamics. Mentors also introduced students

to professional opportunities and networks, such as “Núcleo de Estudantes de Engenharia e Gestão Industrial da Universidade do Minho” (NEEGIUM, the IEM student association) and European Students of Industrial Engineering and Management (ESTIEM). They often shared their academic and career experiences, offering advice and guidance from a recent graduate’s perspective.

4 Students’ perspectives on faculty tutors and *alumni* mentors

This part of the study focus on how students perceived the support and performance provided by faculty tutors and alumni mentors. Data were gathered through questionnaires and focus groups conducted at the end of the semester. With this section, is answered the first research question: “*What are the students’ perspectives regarding the performance of tutors/mentors in PBL context?*”

4.1 Questionnaire results

The online questionnaire is a combined one where the first initial question is for students to indicate which type of tutor they were assessing: the faculty member or the IEM *alumni* mentor. The following sections presents the results.

4.1.1 Faculty tutors

A total of 33 students out of 70 enrolled answered to the questionnaire. The answers came from students in all eight projects teams (G1 to G8), with the distribution of responses per team varied, ranged from 1 (G1) to 6 (G3, G6, and G8), with most answers coming from Groups G2, G3, G5, G6, and G8. In terms of gender, the sample was balanced, with 17 female and 16 male respondents.

As part of the questionnaire, students were asked to rate the overall performance of their faculty tutor on a scale from 1 to 10. The answers showed a broad range of scores, 5.3 to 10, with an average rating of 7.3. In some cases, the evaluation was based on feedback from just one or two students, while in others, several team members contributed to the score, offering a more representative view.

In the open comments, students highlighted several positive aspects of the support provided by their tutors. Many valued the help clarifying the project’s objective, making sense of the peer assessment process and its outcomes, and creating a supportive and collaborative team environment. Some also emphasized the tutor’s role in guiding the team through challenging moments and encouraging thoughtful decision-making. However, feedback regarding availability was more mixed – while some students felt that their tutor was accessible and responsive, others preferred regular contact or proactive engagement. These varied perceptions point to a gap between student expectations and how the tutor’s role was experienced, particularly regarding accessibility and presence throughout the project.

Among the open comments, by one hand, one student praised the tutor’s role in team cohesion, stating: “*The tutor kept the team together during the most difficult moments.*” On the other hand, another student expressed a desire for more consistent support, suggesting the tutor could “*be more present and available to help us through the various challenges we faced.*” These contrasting views reflect the diversity of student expectations and experiences regarding tutor engagement.

4.1.2 IEM *alumni* mentors

A total of 38 students answered to the IEM alumni mentor questionnaire, representing all eight project teams (G1 to G8). The group was slightly female-majority, with 21 female and 17 male students. The number of responses per team ranged from 2 to 8, with the highest participation in Groups G2 and G6.

Students rated their mentor between 4 and 10 on a 10-point scale, with the median score across teams ranging from 6.0 to 9.0 (average score of 8.3). The average ratings were also consistently high, suggesting that students

appreciated the support received from mentors. Some teams showed very consistent responses among members (standard deviation smaller than 1), while others had a wider spread of opinions. This variation may reflect differences in how mentors interacted with their teams or how students interpreted their role. Overall, data suggest that the alumni mentors played a valuable role in guiding and supporting first-year students throughout the project experience.

The open-ended answers paint a largely positive picture of the mentors' involvement. Students frequently praised the mentors for their support in clarifying doubts and offering guidance, particularly during stressful or uncertain stages of the project. Comments such as "helped the team stay united," "offered valuable feedback that helped us complete key tasks," and "guided us in the right direction, especially at the beginning of the project" were common. Others highlighted contributions to team motivation and group dynamics: "helped us break the ice and improve communication," and "provided tools that really helped us work better as a team." These examples suggest that while mentors may not have been perceived as highly visible in terms of formal coordination or academic leadership, their peer-level presence and emotional support were valued.

When asked whether their expectations had been met, most students responded positively. However, a few noted that they would have appreciated a more consistent presence from the mentor throughout the entire project.

4.2 Focus group results

In the final workshop, students participated in small group discussions and completed feedback sheets on the tutor's role. The form had three parts: 1) the tutor corresponded/not corresponded to the expectations (give examples); 2) the tutor role could be improved: "Yes (e.g. to do some activities with the team)", "No. Why?" and 3) Other suggestions. Figure 2 presents the paper sheet fulfilled by a group of students.

Workshop Final PIEG11 2024_25

PAPEL DO TUTOR

O tutor correspondeu / não correspondeu às expectativas do grupo ... [exemplos - exemplos].
Identifiquem, p.f. se se referem a tutor-docente ou tutor-aluno.

Os tutores não correspondiam às nossas expectativas. Estávamos à espera que tivessem mais ~~emp~~ iniciativa. No entanto, quando pedíamos alguma coisa estavam disponíveis para ajudar. Neste caso referimo-nos aos 2 tutores.

O papel do tutor poderia ser melhorado?

- Sim: Como? (ex. fazer atividades específicas com as equipas, etc.)

- Não: Porquê?

Podiam haver atividades presenciais para criar mais afinidade com os tutores, de modo a ~~o~~ estarmos mais à vontade com eles e solicitar a sua ajuda mais frequentemente.

Outras Sugestões:

Figure 2. Example of completed paper sheet fulfilled by a group of students during the final workshop related to the tutor role (in Portuguese)

The first part of Figure 2 reflected a common issue mentioned by several students: the support they expected from tutors and mentors did not always match what they wanted. In this case, the group felt neither role fully

met their expectations. Although they recognised that both the tutor and mentor were available when needed, they wished they had been more present and involved during the project.

In the second part of the document, the students also suggest that more face-to-face contact could have helped build a better relationship. They wrote *“There could be more face-to-face activities to create more affinity with tutors, so we would feel more comfortable asking for help”*. This shows the importance of building trust early on, so students feel at ease reaching out. The students did not complete the third part of the document, which asked for further suggestions.

In PBL, tutors are not there to give answers or tell students exactly what to do. Their role is to ask questions, help students reflect, and guide them in taking responsibility for their learning. This approach can feel unfamiliar to students used to teaching that is more traditional. Their feedback suggests that explaining the tutor’s role at the beginning – and returning to it during the semester – could help manage expectations and improve the overall experience. However, this was always done by the coordinator.

4.3 Comparing tutor and mentor roles

This section addresses the second research question: “Do tutors and mentors play tutor role similarly?” To answer this research question, the quantitative ratings from Likert-scale questions and open-ended student feedback was analyzed. The comparison of average scores across the complete questionnaire indicates that, while tutors and mentors were positively evaluated overall, students tended to rate mentors slightly higher on several dimensions - particularly those related to motivation, availability, and team dynamics.

Interestingly, slightly more students responded to the mentor evaluation (38) than to the tutor evaluation (33). This difference may reflect the nature of the mentor–student relationship. As recent graduates, mentors may be perceived as more approachable or relatable, which could make students feel more comfortable providing feedback.

To deepen the comparison between tutors and mentors, the 15 items with the most considerable differences in average scores as rated by students were identified. This selection was based purely on numerical differences without prior categorization. The corresponding heatmap (Figure 3, in blue) presents these 15 items, with each row representing one evaluation criterion. The two columns display the average scores for faculty tutors and alumni mentors, respectively, as rated on a 5-point Likert scale. As a result, color intensity (shades of blue) indicates the level of agreement, with darker tones reflecting higher average scores within each role, rather than absolute comparison across columns. This visual representation makes it easier to identify where perceptions of tutor and mentor support diverged most significantly. Upon reviewing the selected items, several recurring themes emerged – such as communication clarity, team motivation, emotional support, and resource guidance – which help frame the differing contributions of each role.

The standard deviation heatmap (Figure 3, in orange) adds another layer to the analysis by highlighting the consistency of student answers across the 15 evaluation items. While most evaluations were generally positive, student ratings showed more variation in some points for both tutors and mentors. The lower values indicate more agreement among students, suggesting a shared support experience, whereas higher values point to more varied opinions among students. This visual representation helps identify which aspects of tutor or mentor support were experienced consistently by most students and which may have been perceived differently across teams – possibly due to individual engagement, communication style, or student expectations about each role.

Among all the evaluation items, only one was rated higher for tutors than for mentors: "*The tutor discusses the results of the peer assessments with the team.*" This likely reflects the more formal role that tutors play in coordinating and supporting the peer evaluation process within the academic framework.

Creates a safe environment for sharing ideas	4.18	4.87	0.88	0.47
Clarifies doubts about PBL process	4.03	4.68	0.98	0.57
Supports the team in achieving goals	4.12	4.66	0.86	0.71
Shows concern for individual learning	3.88	4.39	0.82	0.95
Monitors balanced use of resources	3.97	4.47	1.10	1.06
Communicates clearly	4.24	4.74	0.83	0.60
Encourages critical analysis	4.06	4.55	0.97	0.55
Shows enthusiasm for the tutor role	4.00	4.47	1.12	0.83
Views students as responsible for their learning	4.24	4.71	0.75	0.57
Knows available project resources	4.09	4.55	0.80	0.69
Encourages individual study	3.79	4.24	0.86	1.00
Acts to energize team and report status	3.76	4.18	1.00	1.23
Encourages students to follow project plan	4.18	4.61	0.81	0.72
Helps refocus when team loses direction	4.03	4.45	1.05	0.86
Guides team when external info is needed	4.24	4.61	0.83	0.75
	Tutor Mean	Mentor Mean	Tutor SD	Mentor SD

Figure 3. Heatmap: Faculty Tutor vs. IEM alumni Mentor Evaluation (15 items with higher difference). Mean scores in blue, Standard Deviation in orange

To better understand how students saw the roles of tutors and mentors, their answers to the open-ended questions in the questionnaire were revised. Their comments gave valuable insight into what kind of support each role provided during the project. Table 2 summarizes these differences, highlighting how students described tutors' and mentors' focus, interaction style, and contributions - supported by short quotes in their own words.

Students tended to see tutors and mentors as having different yet complementary roles. Tutors were generally linked to academic support, especially in helping teams stay focused on learning goals and managing the project's structure. Conversely, mentors came across as more approachable and informal - someone the team could turn to for motivation, emotional support, and practical tips based on real experience. Both roles were appreciated and met different needs along the students' learning path.

During the focus group, a few students said they wished tutors and mentors had taken more initiative. That comment suggests that some may not fully understand the tutor's purpose. Rather than directing the project or providing solutions, tutors guide when asked and encourage students to take responsibility for their own learning. Even though this was explained at the beginning of the semester and reinforced along the way, not all students seemed to grasp it. It shows how important it is to set expectations clearly - and to return to them as the project progresses, especially in a learning model that places autonomy at the centre.

Table 2. Characteristics of the tutors and mentors reported by the students

Characteristics	Tutor	Mentor
Role and focus	Academic support especially related to peer assessment and guiding project structure. <i>"Gave feedback on peer evaluations and asked questions that made us think and research."</i>	Emotional and interpersonal support, especially in times of uncertainty. <i>"Guided us in more stressful moments."</i>
Academic support	Strong emphasis on helping clarify doubts and highlight essential aspects of the project. <i>"Clarified some doubts."</i> <i>"Helped us focus on what really matters and showed the value of teamwork."</i>	More related to report feedback, team management, and soft skills. <i>"Clarified doubts, especially about teamwork and presentations."</i>
Type of interaction	Structured and academically oriented. <i>"Helped interpret the peer assessment process."</i>	Informal, peer-level, and highly accessible. <i>"Helped the team stay united."</i>
Qualifications	Faculty members with subject expertise and project oversight roles. <i>"Having someone with experience to help us"</i>	Recent graduates with first-hand experience in PBL and professional insights. <i>"He helped us to be more organized and improve our relationships between members. He also provided us with tools that contributed greatly to the project."</i>
Goal of the relationship	To guide students in applying academic knowledge and managing learning processes. <i>"Keep the assessment in order as well as the delivery deadlines"</i>	To support students' integration into project work and university life, and offer motivational input. <i>"Give his perspective from when he was in our shoes."</i>
Goal	Help students progress academically through structured feedback and learning autonomy. <i>"The tutor showed interest in the good functioning of the team, in the distribution of tasks and in the team's commitment to the project."</i>	Foster a positive team dynamic and provide practical tips drawn from personal experience. <i>"The detailed information he provided us when we had questions and the feedback on the work the team was doing."</i>

5 Tutors and mentors perspectives: tutoring experience

This section shares what tutors and mentors said about their experience during the project. Their answers to the questionnaire help to understand how they felt in their role and how they viewed the students' involvement. Thus, this section intends to answer the question research 3: "How was the tutoring/mentoring experience?".

The tutors rated this tutoring experience with an average of 3.5 out of 5 points. Regarding the overall experience, the following main aspects emerged: (1) on the positive side, some tutors highlighted the opportunity to interact with students from the first year; and (2) on the negative side, complaints that the students had small interaction with the tutors and does not worked as a team. When looking at tutor's answers about how the students saw their role, 4 out of 6 tutors considered that students saw them as someone who could help them with technical content, something that it is not expected to occur. Surprisingly, only one tutor considered that the team saw her/him as someone more experienced that could help them with the project planning and management and another tutor mentioned that the team saw him/her as a team member.

In general, tutors and mentors considered this an easy task (average rate 4 and 3.75 out of 5 points to the question "Do you consider that being a tutor was an easy task?"). They also considered the teams were proactive (4 out of 6 tutors), not waiting for them replies to proceed in the project. In addition, they considered

the majority of the team members had a responsible attitude toward the project development and were motivated during its development (5 out of 6 tutors). This was not always the case, and for example, regarding the G5 tutoring (score 5.5), both tutor and mentor observed little proactivity and low synergy among the various group members. In the open-ended questions, some confusion was noted regarding the role of the tutors within the team - a student had expectations for the tutor that did not align with their role.

Furthermore, the six tutors that answered to the questionnaire showed that they were available to meet with the teams whenever necessary. They also considered that they supported the team in providing feedback when asked/required (5 out of 6 tutors). They also considered that stimulated their active participation (5 out of 6 tutors), incentivizing the team to research and analyse information about the project (4 out of 6 tutors). In addition, they considered that stimulated their autonomy (3 out of 6 tutors), helping them to distinguish the essential from the accessory (2 out of 6 tutors), helping to comply with the project plans and objectives (1 out of the 6 tutors) and sharing ideas and contacts (1 out of 6 tutors).

6 Conclusions

PBL has gained increasing recognition as an effective pedagogical approach in higher education, particularly within the field of IEM. In the context of IEM, where the application of theory to practice is essential, PBL offers students the opportunity to engage in real-world problem solving, collaboration, and hands-on learning. However, the success of PBL is not solely dependent on the design of the projects themselves but also on the support provided to students throughout the process. One of the key components of effective PBL is the role of tutoring and mentoring, which helps to guide students through complex tasks, foster critical thinking, and enhance learning outcomes.

This paper presents the results of a research on the impact of tutoring and mentoring on the success of freshman students in an IEM program during a PBL course. The study explores the approaches in which structured support systems, involving both peer mentoring and faculty tutoring can influence the learning experiences and academic performance of students engaged in project-based activities. By analysing the results of the questionnaires, it was identified some of the benefits: the opportunity to interact with students from the first year. In addition, some challenges were identified, namely, lack of involvement from the students and lack of ability to work as a team, and key success factors, availability for the tutors to meet with the students when necessary.

The tutoring experience allowed for the observation of significant student progress over the course of a semester, from their entry into university. Confidence, teamwork, conflict management, accountability, and public speaking were among the many aspects that improved. Growth was evident both on a personal level and as a team.

Through this study, it was sought to contribute to the growing body of literature on the effectiveness of tutoring and mentoring in PBL, offering insights into how such interventions can enhance student engagement, skill development, and overall educational outcomes. The findings provide valuable information for educators and institutions seeking to improve the learning environment for students entering the field of Industrial Engineering and Management.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia within the R&D Unit Project Scope UID/00319/Centro ALGORITMI (ALGORITMI/UM).

References

- Alves, A. C., Moreira, F., Leão, C. P. & Teixeira, S. (2017). Tutoring experiences in PBL of Industrial Engineering and Management program: teachers vs students. *ASME 2017 International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition (IMECE2016), Volume 5*:
- Alves, A. C., Moreira, F., Leão, C. P., & Fernandes, S. (2020, November 16). Ten Years of Positive Feedback on Project-Based Learning From First-Year Engineering Students' Perspective. *Volume 9: Engineering Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2020-23212>
- Alves, A. C., Moreira, F., Lima, R. M., Sousa, R. M., Carvalho, D., Mesquita, D., Fernandes, S., & Van-Hattum-Janssen, N. (2014). Aprendizagem Baseada em Projetos interdisciplinares: análise da implementação em duas estruturas curriculares distintas. In A. Fischer & O. L. de O. M. Heinig (Eds.), *Linguagens em uso nas Engenharias* (Edifurb-). FURB.
- Alves, A. C., Sousa, R. M., Fernandes, S., Cardoso, E., Carvalho, M. A., Figueiredo, J., & Pereira, R. M. S. (2016). Teacher's experiences in PBL: implications for practice. *European Journal of Engineering Education, 41*(2), 123–141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2015.1023782>
- Alves, A. C., Sousa, R., Moreira, F., Carvalho, M. A., Cardoso, E., Pimenta, P., Malheiro, T., Brito, I., Fernandes, S., & Mesquita, D. (2016). Managing PBL difficulties in an industrial engineering and management program. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management, 9*(3), 586. <https://doi.org/10.3926/jiem.1816>
- Alves, A. C., & van Hattum-Janssen, N. (2022). *Training Engineering Students for Modern Technological Advancement* (Anabela Carvalho Alves & N. van Hattum-Janssen (eds.)). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-8816-1>
- Alves, A.C., & Leão, C. P. (2015). Action, practice and research in project based learning in an industrial engineering and management program. *ASME International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition, Proceedings (IMECE), 5–2015*. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2015-51438>
- Alves, A.C., Moreira, F., Fernandes, S., Leão, C. P., & Sousa, R. (2017). PBL in the first year of an industrial engineering and management program: A journey of continuous improvement. *International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education, 9*, 44–51. <https://hdl.handle.net/1822/67007>
- Alves, A.C., Moreira, F., Leão, C. P., & Carvalho, M. A. (2017). Sustainability and circular economy through PBL: Engineering students' perceptions. In C. Vilarinho, F. Castro, & M. de L. Lopes (Eds.), *WASTES – Solutions, Treatments and Opportunities II* (pp. 409–415). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315206172-64>
- Alves, A.C., Moreira, F., Lima, R., Sousa, R., Dinis-Carvalho, J., Mesquita, D., Fernandes, S., & Van Hattum-Janssen, N. (2012). Project based learning in first year, first semester of industrial engineering and management: Some results. *ASME International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition, Proceedings (IMECE), 5*, 111–120. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2012-89046>
- Alves, AC, Moreira, F., & Sousa, R. R. (2007). O papel dos tutores na aprendizagem baseada em projectos: três anos de experiência na Escola de Engenharia da Universidade do Minho. *Libro de Actas Do Congreso Internacional Galego-Portugués de Psicopedagogía. A.Coruña/Universidade Da Coruña: Revista Galego-Portuguesa de Psicología e Educación., 1*, 1759–1770. <http://repositorium.sdum.uminho.pt/handle/1822/18278>
- Alves, Anabela C., Abreu, M. F., & Leão, C. P. (2024). Sustainable Solutions for Fast Fashion Waste: A Project-Based Learning Approach. *Volume 7: Engineering Education*, Submitted. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2024-145535>
- Alves, Anabela C., Moreira, F., Leão, C. P., & Teixeira, S. (2017). Tutoring Experiences in PBL of Industrial Engineering and Management Program: Teachers vs Students. *Volume 5: Education and Globalization, 5*, V005T06A008. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2017-71306>
- Alves, Anabela Carvalho, Fernandes, S., Moreira, F., Lima, R. M. S. P., Carvalho, J. D. A., Sousa, R. M. A. S., Mesquita, D. I. A., & Hattum-Janssen, N. van. (2021). *Project-Based Learning: implementação no primeiro ano de um curso de Engenharia*. UMinho Editora. <https://doi.org/10.21814/uminho.ed.26>
- Alves, Anabela, Moreira, F., & Sousa, R. (2010). Aprendizagem baseada em Projectos Interdisciplinares em Engenharia Industrial: dissimilitudes de tutoria entre o início e o final do curso. *PAEE2010-International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education, 1*, 133–139. <https://hdl.handle.net/1822/19196>
- Breque, M., Nul, L. De, & Petridis, A. (2021). *Industry 5.0: Towards a sustainable, human-centric and resilient European industry*. <https://doi.org/10.2777/308407>
- Colombo, C. R., Moreira, F., & Alves, A. C. (2015). Sustainability Education in PBL Education: the case study of IEM. *Proceedings of the Project Approaches in Engineering Education*, 221–228.
- Colvin, J. W., & Ashman, M. (2010). Roles, Risks, and Benefits of Peer Mentoring Relationships in Higher Education. *Mentoring & Tutoring: Partnership in Learning, 18*(2), 121–134. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13611261003678879>
- Fernandes, S., Flores, M. A., & Lima, R. M. (2009). *A tutoria no contexto do Project-Led Education (PLE): potencialidades e desafios* (pp. 89–113).
- Figueiredo, A. D. de. (2023). Educating Engineers for Turbulent Times. In R. Vasconcelos, A. Alves, C. P. Leao, V. Carvalho, & R. M. Lima (Eds.), *5th International Conference of the Portuguese Society for Engineering Education* (pp. 5-7 july). School of Engineering, University of Minho Press. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27427.02084>
- Grunefeld, H., & Silén, C. (2000). *Problem based learning compared to project organized learning*.
- Leão, C. P., Abreu, M. F., Alves, A. C., & Fernandes, S. (2022). PBL tutoring dynamics in first-year of Industrial Engineering and Management Program. *PAEE/ALE'2022, International Conference on Active Learning in Engineering Education*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7061886>
- Lima, R. M., Carvalho, D., Assunção Flores, M., & Van Hattum-Janssen, N. (2007). A case study on project led education in engineering: students' and teachers' perceptions. *European Journal of Engineering Education, 32*(3), 337–347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043790701278599>
- Lima, R. M., Villas-Boas, V., Soares, F., Carneiro, O. S., Ribeiro, P., & Mesquita, D. (2024). Mapping the implementation of active learning approaches in a school of engineering – the positive effect of teacher training. *European Journal of Engineering Education, 49*(5), 945–964. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2024.2313541>

- Lorenzetti, D. L., Shipton, L., Nowell, L., Jacobsen, M., Lorenzetti, L., Clancy, T., & Paolucci, E. O. (2019). A systematic review of graduate student peer mentorship in academia. *Mentoring & Tutoring: Partnership in Learning*, 27(5), 549–576. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13611267.2019.1686694>
- Majeed, A., & Hwang, S. O. (2024). Making Large Language Models More Reliable and Beneficial: Taking ChatGPT as a Case Study. *Computer*, 57(3), 101–106. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MC.2023.3327028>
- Moreira, F., Mesquita, D., & van Hattum-Janssen, N. Van. (2011). The importance of the project theme in Project-Based Learning: a study of student and teacher perceptions. *Proceedings of the 2011 Project Approaches in Engineering Education*, 53(9). <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781107415324.004>
- Powell, P. C. (2004). Assessment of team-based projects in project-led education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 29(2), 221–230. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043790310001633205>
- Powell, P., & Weenk, W. (2003). *Project-Led Engineering Education*. Lemma Publishers.
- Rahayu, S. (2023). The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Education: Opportunities and Challenges. *Jurnal Educatio FKIP UNMA*, 9(4), 2132–2140. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.31949/educatio.v9i4.6110>
- Ravaglia, R. (2024). *AI Agents Will Shape Every Aspect Of Education In 2025*. Education. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/rayravaglia/2024/12/26/ai-agents-will-shape-every-aspect-of-education-in-2025/>
- Schmier, L. (2001). *Random Thought: A Sacred Trust*. Atwood Publishing. <http://www.halcyon.com/arborhts/rt/01may23.htm>
- Simão, A. M. V., Flores, M. A., Fernandes, S., & Figueira, C. (2008). Tutoria no Ensino Superior. *Sísifo - Revista de Ciências Da Educação*, 7, 75–88. <http://sisifo.fpce.ul.pt>
- Simão, A. M. V., Flores, M. A., Fernandes, S., & Figueira, C. (2015). Tutoring in higher education: Concepts and practices. *Sísifo Educ. Sci. J.*, 7, 73–86.
- Terrion, J. L., & Leonard, D. (2007). A taxonomy of the characteristics of student peer mentors in higher education: findings from a literature review. *Mentoring & Tutoring: Partnership in Learning*, 15(2), 149–164. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13611260601086311>
- Weenk, W., Govers, E., & Vlas, H. (2004). Training in project-based education: practise as you preach. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 29(4), 465–475. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043790410001716301>